

Monotheism of the Divine Names and Attributes as a Defining Criterion of Salafism

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Abstract

This study examines how Saudi Salafism, as a modern ideological construct, has gradually linked the theological teachings about the monotheism of the Divine names and attributes (*tawḥīd al-asmā' wa-l-ṣifāt*) of the Ḥanbalī scholar Ibn Taymiyya (1263–1328) with the teachings of his later Ḥanbalī fellow Muḥammad b. 'Abd al-Wahhāb (1703/04–1792). Within this process, the topic has been turned from a peripheral one into a crucial criterion of defining “Salafī-ness” as such. In this sense, to be a Salafī means to be a follower of the Divine names and attributes in the Ḥanbalī interpretation of Ibn Taymiyya as opposed to the mainstream Ash'arī (and Māturīdī) theology. This criterion, as the authors argue, has been instrumentalized as a tool of claiming one's legitimacy and superiority.

Keywords

Islamic theology – Salafism – Wahhābism – Ibn Taymiyya – Muḥammad b. 'Abd al-Wahhāb – Divine names and attributes – *tawḥīd* – *tawḥīd al-asmā' wa-l-ṣifāt* – Ash'arī theology – Ḥanbalī school

Introducing the Topic and Goals

Those who have labeled themselves as Salafis throughout Islamic history have done so on the basis of many variables, be they beliefs, jurisprudence, way of life, political thought or social ideas. The diversity in their ranks has posed problems for academics who have sought to define Salafism as such, especially from a broader perspective of Islamic reform and its multiplicity. To prevent any potential misunderstanding arising from varied interpretations of this term in the academic literature, we must first clarify what we mean by “Salafism”. The term is rather problematic, as it is not frequently used in Islamic terminology as an abstract noun. Instead, Muslims who refer to the early Muslim community (*salaf*) express this relation either simply by the adjective Salafi or by emphasizing their adherence to the community in their methodology (*madhhab al-salaf, manhaj/minhāj al-salaf, tariqat al-salaf*, among others). They might understand by it a distinct legal methodology, theology, or even, more vaguely, a reformist approach in dealing with modernity. Owing to this variety of approaches, scholars differ in their understanding of Salafism, and specifically in whether it is seen as an ideology, theology, or a specific movement.¹

Our argument is that what today’s Salafis have in common and what largely defines them is not creed (‘*aqīda*) as such, as this is too broad a term, but a subcategory of it which is concerned with the “monotheism of the Divine names and attributes” (*tawhīd al-asmā’ wa-l-ṣifāt*). This includes their adherence to the theological methodology of Ibn Taymiyya in interpreting the Divine names and attributes according to the methodology of the Salaf and turning it into a criterion defining the proper “Salafi-ness” of individual Muslims. This instrumentalization has been so successful that through the influence of Saudi religious institutions, scholarship and proselytizing activities, this

1 For example, Haykel proposes that Salafism can be understood by looking at three constitutive elements of the movement: theology (encapsulated by the concept of *tawhīd*), law (centred on the question of *ijtihād* and adherence to a particular school of law), and politics (determined by a particular *manhaj* – i.e., a general methodology of applying “Salafi” theological teachings, which, as such, also refers to political thought and action). He states that in matters of theology, the movement’s members appear to be in unanimous agreement on the credal tenets that define Salafism. By theology he means, among other things, the emphasis on a particular understanding of *tawhīd*, which Salafis divide into at least three categories: the Oneness of Lordship (*tawhīd al-rubūbiyya*), the Oneness of Godship (*tawhīd al-ulūhiyya*), and the Oneness of the names and attributes (*tawhīd al-asmā’ wa-l-ṣifāt*). See Bernard Haykel, “On the Nature of Salafi Thought and Action”, in *Global Salafism: Islam’s New Religious Movement*, ed. Roel Meijer (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2009), 33–57. We prefer to translate the term “*tawhīd*” as “monotheism” as we believe this closely aligns with the original meaning. As exemplified by Haykel and others – most recently Farid Suleiman in *Ibn Taymiyya and the Attributes of God* (Leiden: Brill, 2024) – “oneness” can also be used.

particular criterion has been adopted by today's Salafis of various ideological backgrounds, be they senior Saudi 'ulamā', advocates of political engagement and activism, apolitical Ahl al-ḥadīth, or violent Jihadīs of al-Qā'ida, Jabhat al-nuṣra and ISIS.² In this sense, to be a Salafī means to be a follower of the Divine names and attributes in the Ḥanbalī interpretation of Ibn Taymiyya (and his disciple Ibn al-Qayyim) as opposed to the mainstream Ash'arī (and Māturīdī) theology.³ The point is that the adjective Ḥanbalī is nowadays used to denote only the legal school, while the "Ḥanbalī" theology is referred to as "Salafī". To illustrate this point about semantic distinctions, Ibn Bāz (d. 1999), after being asked whether it is true that only Ḥanbalīs are Salafis, answered that Salafis are Ḥanafis, Mālikīs, Shāfi'īs and others (i.e., non-madhhabī Ahl al-ḥadīth) who follow the Qur'ān and the Sunna in the fields of *tawḥīd* and *tawḥīd al-asmā' wa-l-ṣifāt*.⁴

2 We do not have space in this article to go into details about these various groupings across the current Salafī spectrum. Let us instead provide just a few examples which can illustrate our point: Rif'at Sayyid Aḥmad, *Rasā'il Juhaymān al-'Utaybī qā'id al-muqtaḥimīn lil-masjid al-ḥarām bi-Makka* (Cairo: Madbuli, 2004), 93–136; Abū 'Ādil 'Azzām, *Mawsū'at dhakhā'ir al-'izām fīmā uṭhira 'an al-imām al-humām al-shahīd 'Abdallāh 'Azzām* (Peshawar: Markaz al-Shahīd 'Azzām al-I'lāmī, 1997), vol. 1, 2; Abū Muḥammad 'Aṣim al-Maqdisī, *Hādhihi 'aqīdatunā* (Manbar al-tawḥīd wa-l-jihād, 2nd edition, 2003); *Dabiq* 2 (AH 1435), 23 and *Dabiq* 8 (AH 1436), 54; *Nubdha 'ammā na'taqīduh wa-nadīn Allāh bihi* (al-Manāra al-Bayḍā': Jabhat al-Nuṣra, n.d.); Muḥammad Quṭb, *Rakā'iz al-īmān* (Cairo: Dār al-Shurūq, 2001); 'Abd al-Raḥmān 'Abd al-Khāliq, *Masā'il al-īmān* (Hawally: Bayt al-Maqdis, 2008), vol. 1, 24–29; 'Alā' Bakr, *Malāmiḥ ra'ṣiyya lil-manhaj al-salafī, muḥāḍarāt fi l-salafīyya* (Alexandria: Dār al-'Aqīda: 2002).

3 It must be duly noted that some Salafī senior scholars such as al-'Uthaymīn, Ibn Jibrīn and Ibn Fawzān used Ibn Qudāma's treatise *Lum'at al-i'tiqād* for the purpose of teaching the creed and *tawḥīd al-asmā' wa-l-ṣifāt*, mostly for beginner and advanced students of theology. However, many others have criticized this approach on the basis that Ibn Qudāma employs a theological method of *tafwīḍ*, which Ibn Taymiyya considered to be invalid. In his short reflections on this controversy, 'Alā' Ḥasan Ismā'īl explains that, for the purpose of teaching the fundamentals of creed, the treatise achieves its goals. This was the reason al-'Uthaymīn did not expound on *tafwīḍ* in his commentary on the book. See *Tafwīḍ al-imām Ibn Qudāma bayn al-mu'ayyidīn wa-l-mu'arīḍīn* (<https://salafcenter.org/7382/>). For Māturīdī theology, see Philipp Bruckmayr, "Salafī Challenge and Māturīdī Response: Contemporary Disputes over the Legitimacy of Māturīdī *Kalām*", *WI* 60:2/3 (2020), 293–326. Moreover, books of other scholars have been appropriated, such as Ibn Khuzayma (d. 923), and even al-Ash'arī himself, whose works on the Divine names and attributes were interpreted in accordance with Ibn Taymiyya's doctrine.

4 See Ibn Bāz, "Laysa al-ḥanābila hum al-salafīyyūn faqat", *Majmū'at fatāwā wa-maqālāt mutanawwi'a*, ed. Muḥammad al-Shuway'ir (Riyadh: Dār al-Qāsim, 1999), vol. 9, 238. The fatwa is undated. It must also be noted that some followers of the Ḥanbalī school of law outside Saudi Arabia criticized Ibn Taymiyya's theological views as adopted and promoted by Salafis; see Muṣṭafā Ḥammūd 'Ulayyān, *al-Sāda al-ḥanābila wa-ikhtilāfuhum ma'a al-salafīyya al-mu'āshira* (Amman: Dār al-Nūr, 2014).

The process whereby the theme of the Divine names and attributes went from being a peripheral topic to a central part of Salafism is part of the story of the rebranding of “Wahhābism”⁵ as “Salafism”, as told by Lauzière in his groundbreaking monograph *The Making of Salafism*.⁶ Lauzière challenges the notion that “Salafism” is a timeless and unchanging phenomenon which can be used as a heuristic device for making sense of the past. Instead, he argues that the term has been used in various ways, with different groups adopting the label to describe their particular approach to Islam, yet it has never been a recognizable concept, let alone a movement. The contemporary understanding of it as a strictly puritanical form of Islam is, according to Lauzière, a relatively recent phenomenon of the 20th century. The concept of “purist Salafism” developed over several decades, especially in the context of decolonization, and, beginning in the 1970s, constructed an all-encompassing and rigorist notion of Islamic purity in order to strengthen and unite Muslims from different regions.⁷ While Lauzière attempts to trace Salafism as a modern phenomenon by focusing on the Arabic abstract term *salafīyya* and the struggle over the meaning of the “Salafism” category, we will focus on how the adjective “Salafī”, in the narrow meaning of Ibn Taymiyya’s view, became a defining criterion of Saudi Salafism that was adopted by many others under the influence of Saudi religious scholarship.

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- 5 Wahhābism is a name for the movement initiated by the Ḥanbalī scholar Muḥammad b. ‘Abd al-Wahhāb. The term was used oftentimes pejoratively, which is also the current narrative of Saudi historiography adopted noncritically by others. However, as we demonstrate in this article, the name was used by Muḥammad b. ‘Abd al-Wahhāb’s followers themselves. On the naming of the Wahhābī movement, see Namira Nahouza, *Wahhabism and the Rise of the New Salafists: Theology, Power and Sunni Islam* (London: I.B. Tauris, 2018), 74–75. According to Nahouza, the insistence by the Wahhābīs on being called Salafīs is tangible from the 1950s and 1970s, and this became even more evident in the last two decades (*ibid.*, 77). In academic parlance, some leading scholars in the field, such as Madawi Al-Rasheed, use the term Wahhābism in reference to the ideological and political use of religion in Saudi Arabia. Al-Rasheed calls it “Wahhabi religio-political discourse.” By that, she means that Wahhābism became a religious discourse used by political authority against society and a weapon wielded by society against its authority. It propagates religious interpretations that require subservience to political authority. Madawi Al-Rasheed, *Contesting the Saudi State: Islamic Voices from a New Generation* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2007), 1 and 26.
- 6 Henri Lauzière, *The Making of Salafism: Islamic Reform in the Twentieth Century* (New York: Columbia University Press, 2015). For a survey of reactions to Lauzière, see Wasim Shiliwala, “Constructing a Textual Tradition: Salafī Commentaries on *al-‘Aqīda al-ṭahāwīyya*”, *WT* 58:4 (2018), 463–65.
- 7 See also Weismann, who has contributed to our knowledge of “enlightened Salafism”, and who aptly proposes distinguishing between a narrower and broader definition of Salafism and speaks about the convergence of the two tendencies. By the former, he means Ḥanbalī-Salafī theology. See Itzchak Weismann, “A Perverted Balance: Modern Salafism between Reform and Jihād”, *WT* 57:1 (2017), 33–66.

There are, of course, other approaches to understanding and working with the label “Salafism”. Bruckmayr and Hartung, while focusing on this phenomenon in its various manifestations, rightly question the prevalent assumption that it is derived unidirectionally from Wahhābī Islam as well as the claim that all the things “Salafī” originate from Saudi Arabia. Rather, they subscribe to the idea that the phenomenon encompassed by the label “Salafism” is diverse and fragmented. On the basis of this view, essentially, “Salafism” can be understood as a political ideology with various subdivisions whose ambition is to engage with structures of governance. Its adherents should be called Salafists. Then there exists the “Salafī” Islam adhered to by “Salafis”, who put much more stress on individual purity regardless of the sociopolitical context.⁸

We consider both labels – namely the proper nouns “Salafī” and “Salafist” – to be legitimate, although the boundary between the groupings they describe is often blurred. As for the Muslims who identify with this aspect of Islam, as we mentioned, they typically do not frequently use the abstract term “Salafism” (*salafīyya*). Instead, they tend to employ the adjective “Salafī” (such as Salafī school, methodology, call, etc.), primarily referring to the theology of the Divine names and attributes.⁹ However, the fact that they all use the term in this sense results from a monopolization and redefinition of this label, aligning

8 Philipp Bruckmayr and Jan-Peter Hartung, “Introduction: Challenges from “The Periphery”? – Salafī Islam Outside the Arab World. Spotlights on Wider Asia” *WT* 60:2/3 (2020), 137–69. The view that “Salafism” is not a singular ideology is also suggested by others; see, for example, Justyna Nedza, “Salafismus” – Überlegungen zur Schärfung einer Analysekatgorie”, in *Salafismus: Auf der Suche nach dem wahren Islam*, ed. Behnam T. Said and Hazim Fouad (Freiburg: Herder, 2014), 80–105; or Daniel Lav, *Radical Islam and the Revival of Medieval Theology* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2012).

9 When the term *salafīyya* is used in Arabic, it is commonly employed either as a calque of Salafism (of course, with similar vagueness) or synonymously with the Salafī school or methodology, in contrast to Ash‘arī theology. According to al-Sihīmī, who explains the terminology in his popular booklet about who is a true Salafī, the term *salafīyya* is used by Ibn Taymiyya in some of his books for those who advocate the opinion of “Salaf” regarding God’s transcendence (*fawqīyya*). To al-Sihīmī, *salafī*, *salafīyyūn* and *salafīyya* are all acceptable terms – see ‘Abd al-Salām b. Sālīm b. Rajā’ al-Sihīmī, *Kun salafīyyan ‘alā al-jādida* (Cairo: Dār al-Minhāj, 2005), 43–44. In premodern times, the term *salafīyya* was used to denote a particular theological group. For example, when Ibn Taymiyya – rarely – uses the term *salafīyya*, it is to denote those Sunnis who affirmed the Divine names and attributes, yet without resorting to *tashbih*. See, for example, Ibn Taymiyya, *Dar’ ta‘arūḍ al-‘aql wa-l-naql*, ed. Muḥammad Rashād Sālīm (Riyadh: Jāmi‘at al-Imām Su‘ūd al-Islāmiyya, Wizārat al-Ta‘līm al-Thānī, 1991), vol. 2, 8. It is interesting to note that, for example, al-Shahrastānī (d. 1153) uses the term *salafīyya* in the sense of a theological school within imāmī Shī‘a as opposed to *mushabbīha*, yet in general this usage seems rather scarce. See al-Shahrastānī, *Kitāb al-mīlāl wa-l-nihāl*, ed. Muḥammad ‘Abd al-Qādir al-Fāḍilī (Saida: al-Maktaba al-‘Aṣriyya, 2005), 133.

it with the Ḥanbalī theological perspective modelled on Ibn Taymiyya. This process of redefinition itself is thus one aspect of the modern phenomenon known as Salafism.

But still, as we mostly deal with theology, we prefer the more neutral noun “Salafī”. As should be clear by now, in this article, we use the term “Salafism” to denote a specific Sunnī interpretation of Islam associated with modern Saudi proselytizing activities and adopted by various individuals and movements worldwide, regardless of their loyalty or opposition to the Saudi regime. We look at Salafism not as a continuum of medieval and modern reformist Islam, but rather as a modern ideological construct, connected initially with Saudi Arabia, which instrumentalized the Islamic intellectual legacy by adopting a narrow definition of what it is to be a Salafī, that is essentially a Ḥanbalī (in the theological sense of the word) elitist position of understanding the monotheism of the Divine names and attributes. By doing so, they also imposed this understanding on various streams of Salafism.

As for the term “Ḥanbalī”, it is used in this article in two essential meanings and this duality is crucial for understanding our argument.¹⁰ First, it refers to a school of law; second, it denotes a theological school. In the latter sense, it is predominantly employed in medieval parlance, but not exclusively, as demonstrated by examples we provide later on. Ibn Taymiyya is unequivocally the pivotal figure in the construction of modern Salafism. He was a Ḥanbalī scholar in both meanings of the term, yet he criticized affiliation with a particular school (*taqlīd, al-ta‘aṣṣub al-madhhabī*) and advocated *ijtihād*. He termed this approach as “salafī”. Furthermore, he used the term “salafī” to describe his theological approach. Some Salafīs were inspired by both aspects of his teachings (such as the modern Ahl al-ḥadīth), while others were influenced solely by his theology (i.e., regardless of their *madhhabī* affiliation or claiming *ijtihād*).

For example, Shiliwala in his reflections on the Salafī *‘aqīda* mentions that they highlight and comment on only a few doctrinal works, often “from the Ḥanbalī school, that presents doctrines very close to (if not identical with) the Salafī creed. Common examples include Ibn Qudāma’s *Lum‘at al-‘itiqād*, Ibn Taymiyya’s *al-‘Aqīda al-wāsiṭiyya*, and Ibn ‘Abd al-Wahhāb’s *Kitāb al-tawḥīd*.”¹¹ Then he states that one work stands out as a subject of commentary, that is *al-‘Aqīda al-ṭahāwiyya* by a Ḥanafī jurist at-Ṭahāwī. He claims that the creed was

¹⁰ See W. Montgomery Watt, *Islamic Philosophy and Theology: An Extended Survey* (Edinburgh: Edinburgh University Press, 1985), 98. For Ḥanbalī Islām, see George Makdisi, “Hanbalite Islam”, in *Studies on Islam*, trans. and ed. Merlin L. Swartz (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 1981).

¹¹ Shiliwala, “Constructing a Textual Tradition”, 470.

appropriated by Salafis via a commentary of Ibn Abī l-‘Izz, who, albeit a Ḥanafī jurist, was influenced by Ibn Taymiyya and his circle, and his commentary can be described as Salafī. This supports our claim that Saudi Salafism is defined by the adoption of Ḥanbalī theology (Ibn Abī l-‘Izz was a Ḥanbalī in theology, in the medieval parlance), of which Ibn Taymiyya is the cornerstone.

In academic literature, it is often taken for granted that in Salafism a trichotomic conception of *tawḥīd* has always been present in this form, and that this conception was promoted by Ibn Taymiyya¹² and later on by Muḥammad b. ‘Abd al-Wahhāb. We believe that this erroneous view distorts the narrative revolving around Salafism. The trichotomic conception, for the sake of argument, is as follows: 1) belief in God as the only Creator of all things (i.e., *tawḥīd al-rubūbiyya*), 2) worship must therefore be rendered solely to him (i.e., *tawḥīd al-ulūhiyya*) to avoid the sin of polytheism (*shirk*),¹³ 3) God can only be known by His names and attributes (*tawḥīd al-asmā’ wa-l-ṣifāt*), which are by nature mostly anthropomorphic (He has hands, He sees and hears, He is sitting on His throne, etc.) and by which He described Himself in the Qur’ān and ḥadīth without resorting to allegoric interpretation.¹⁴ For the sake of clarity, it must be noted that *tawḥīd*, which deals only with theological issues, is part of a broader concept of *‘aqīda* (pl. *‘aqā’id*), which deals with the creed as such. It might distinguish Salafis from other Muslims, yet they themselves may hold different positions. However, in the Salafī Ash‘arī medieval polemics, theology of the Divine names and attributes has been the most debated and controversial issue, perhaps together with the question of whether one’s deeds are to be judged in considering one’s belief (*īmān*).¹⁵

By giving evidence from Salafī literature¹⁶ of various provenience, we argue in this article that the trichotomic conception of Ibn Taymiyya was adopted and integrated with the teachings of Muḥammad b. ‘Abd al-Wahhāb only

12 In fact, Ibn Taymiyya himself occasionally employed a dichotomic *tawḥīd*, where *tawḥīd al-asmā’ wa-l-ṣifāt* constituted a part of *tawḥīd al-rubūbiyya*. As the discussion surrounding this topic grew contentious, it evolved into a trichotomic division; see ‘Abd al-‘Azīz b. ‘Abdallāh al-Rājihī, *Tawfīq rabb al-‘ibād fī sharḥ kitāb taḥrīr al-i’tiqād ‘an adrān al-ilḥād lil-Ṣan‘ānī* (Dammam: Dār Ibn al-Jawzī, 1430/2009), 32.

13 In modern Salafist discourse, *shirk* may have many forms, such as veneration of graves and necrolatry, non-Islamic government, or democracy.

14 For a brief survey of Ibn Taymiyya’s theological position on this matter, see Merlin L. Swartz, “A Seventh-Century A.H. Sunnī Creed: The *Aqīda Wāsiṭiyya* of Ibn Taymiyya”, *Humaniora Islamica* 2 (1974), 91–131. For Ibn Taymiyya’s opinions in Arabic, see Muṣṭafā ‘Abd al-Qādir ‘Aṭā (ed.), *Kitāb al-asmā’ wa-l-ṣifāt lil-īmām al-‘allāma Taqī al-Dīn b. Taymiyya* (Beirut: Dār al-Kutub al-‘Ilmiyya, 1998), 2 vols.

15 As duly noted by Shiliwala, “Constructing a Textual Tradition”, 497–99.

16 We prefer the term Salafī here because our analysis also includes early Wahhābī literature, which predates the modern phenomenon referred to in academic literature as Salafism.

gradually. Moreover, the theology of the Divine names and attributes became accented in Salafi parlance in the context of claiming its own legitimacy while discrediting others. In this respect, we show some examples of how and why it has been instrumentalized.

We would like this article to shed more light on this neglected aspect in the study of Salafism as a modern phenomenon. Scholars who focus on contemporary Salafism tend to be mostly preoccupied with aspects related to politics, the use of violence and proselytizing activities.¹⁷ Theology is mostly addressed in so far as it can explain the use of violence, terrorism and politics. Consequently, the available studies are rather preoccupied with topics such as excommunication (*takfīr*), loyalty and disavowal (*al-walāʾ wa-l-barāʾ*), or *ḥākimiyya*, which is part of *tawḥīd al-ulūhiyya* (or even *al-rubūbiyya*),¹⁸ the aspect of *tawḥīd* that is most prone to new ideological reinterpretations, but not with the monotheism of the Divine names and attributes. There are certain exceptions, such as Nahouza, who dealt with the topic of the Divine names and attributes in her monograph *Wahhabism and the Rise of the New Salafists*. She states that “The focus of the book is the theological arguments about God and His Attributes, and the position of the Salafists on these issues.”¹⁹ However, much of her book is devoted to medieval discussion, while her case studies on the debate surrounding the attributes as well as conclusions remain underexplored. Her book deals with theology, but not how it is used as a tool to exercise power, as the title might indicate.

Speaking of medieval discussions, there are excellent studies dealing with the topic that are usually not taken into consideration in the literature on modern Salafism and to which we refer the reader for deeper insight into the topic,²⁰ since we confine ourselves to the ideological mechanism of using theology and avoid its complicated technical language as much as possible in

17 Which is also evident from the famous typology introduced by Quintan Wiktorowicz, “Anatomy of the Salafi Movement”, *Studies in Conflict and Terrorism* 29:3 (2006), 207–39.

18 There also exists the “tetrachotomic” conception of *tawḥīd*, where *ḥākimiyya* features as an independent fourth category, as used, for example, in ‘Abd al-Khāliq, *Masā’il al-īmān*.

19 Nahouza, *Wahhabism*, 10. For a critical assessment of this book see Bernard Haykel’s review in *WI* 60:4 (2020), 506–09.

20 There is a substantial number of studies devoted to the topic of the Divine names and attributes in the medieval period. See, for example, Suleiman, *Ibn Taymiyya and the Attributes of God*, or Merlin Swartz, *A Medieval Critique of Anthropomorphism: Ibn al-Jawzī’s Kitāb Akhbār Aṣ-Ṣifāt* (Leiden: Brill, 2002). The book deals with *Ibn al-Jawzī* (not to be confused with Ibn Qayyim al-Jawziyya) and his deviation from the Ḥanbali position. See also Miriam Ovadia, *Ibn Qayyim al-Jawziyya and the Divine Attributes: Rationalized Traditionalistic Theology* (Boston: Brill, 2018), or Livnat Holtzman, *Anthropomorphism in Islam: The Challenge of Traditionalism (700–1350)* (Edinburgh: Edinburgh University Press, 2018).

order to make the study more accessible to experts of various disciplines. It seems that there is a growing awareness in the literature on Salafism about the importance of the Divine names and attributes. However, the existing literature often adopts the narrative of Saudi Salafism, which leads to much confusion.

The Divine Names and Attributes: from Peripherality to Centrality, from Wahhābism to Salafism

In what follows, we will demonstrate how the conception of the monotheism of the Divine names and attributes developed diachronically in the transition from Wahhābism to Salafism, from peripherality to centrality, and from local to global, while interconnecting the teachings of Muḥammad b. ‘Abd al-Wahhāb with those of Ibn Taymiyya.

Let us begin by explaining what we mean by the peripherality of the Divine names and attributes in the early Wahhābī discourse. First of all, it must be noted that the teachings of Muḥammad b. ‘Abd al-Wahhāb are part of the Ḥanbalī school, whose distinctive feature is that it has been both a legal and a theological school. In the sense of the latter, it has been the archrival of Mu‘tazila and Ash‘arī theology. As Wahhābism originated in the Ḥanbalī milieu in Najd,²¹ it is therefore logical that the movement was aware of the Ḥanbalī theological legacy early on and subscribed to it. Nevertheless, the monotheism of the Divine names and attributes, a scholastic topic par excellence, was quite peripheral if we are to consider Muḥammad b. ‘Abd al-Wahhāb’s general conception of *tawḥīd*, which was dichotomic. Michael Cook, who studied early Wahhābism, notes quite aptly that the domain of *al-asmā’ wa-l-ṣifāt* is “a domain as central to early Ḥanbalism as it was peripheral to Wahhābism.”²² Cook’s note is still valid, but it must be qualified. It seems that Muhammad b. ‘Abd al-Wahhāb was not interested much in theology in its complexity, including the monotheism of the Divine names and attributes as a superior theological issue. He focused rather on the simple beliefs of *‘aqīda*. This matter is reflected in his dichotomic conception of *tawḥīd rubūbī* and *tawḥīd*

21 Najd is a central part of the Arabian Peninsula. For its religious history and Ḥanbalism, see U. M. Al-Juhany, *Najd before the Salafi Reform Movement: Social, Political, and Religious Conditions during the Three Centuries Preceding the Rise of the Saudi State* (Ithaca Press with King Abdul Aziz Foundation, 2002). In Saudi historiography, the “pre-Salafi” religious scholars are referred to as imams of the Najdī mission (*a‘immat al-da‘wa al-najdiyya*).

22 Michael Cook, “On the Origins of Wahhābism”, *Journal of the Royal Asiatic Society* 2:2 (1992), 191–202, footnote 72.

ulūhī. The first means that God is the Creator, while the latter expresses the idea of the monotheism of worship, ridding oneself of *shirk*, abandoning the worship of anything but God, and disowning nonbelievers and regarding them as enemies.²³ In this respect, he focused on aspects of proper worship and fighting *shirk* in deeds and words.

In *Kitāb al-tawhīd*, a seminal work on the topic by Muḥammad b. ‘Abd al-Wahhāb, the theme of the Divine names and attributes is also peripheral. As ‘Abdallāh Ṣāliḥ al-‘Uthaymīn, a renowned Saudi historian,²⁴ aptly puts it:

Muḥammad b. ‘Abd al-Wahhāb finishes the book with a somewhat long chapter in which he touches upon the subject of the belief in the unity of God in His names and attributes. He quotes a verse from the Qur’ān and traditions in which God is spoken of as having fists, fingers and hand, and of being on His throne. However, these are theological problems that the shaykh did not wish to enter into here, and so he reserved treatment of them for later works. The *Kitāb al-tawhīd* was written for a community in which there was no development of intellectual speculations, and the serious problem, in the Shaykh’s view, was that his people had been practicing things contrary to the unity of God in their worship.²⁵

What, then, are those “later works”? In the same book, ‘Abdallāh Ṣāliḥ al-‘Uthaymīn mentions *Uṣūl al-īmān*. He describes the book as dealing with the topic of the Divine names and attributes.²⁶ However, the treatise itself is relatively short and the topic is dealt with only very superficially, as in his other treatises. Moreover, it seems that the treatise was elaborated by some of Ibn ‘Abd al-Wahhāb’s sons.²⁷

When describing Muḥammad b. ‘Abd al-Wahhāb’s conception of *tawhīd*, Nahouza disregards the common dichotomic conception found in his works. Instead, she argues that he drew inspiration for his definition from the teachings of Ibn Taymiyya. Accordingly, it consists of three parts, the third being *tawhīd al-ṣifāt*. Yet she acknowledges that this part evolved into *tawhīd*

23 Ahmad S. Dallal, *Islam Without Europe: Traditions of Reform in Eighteenth-Century Islamic Thought* (Chapel Hill, NC: University of North Carolina Press, 2018), 25.

24 Not to be confused with his relative, the famous Saudi senior shaykh Muḥammad b. Ṣāliḥ al-‘Uthaymīn (d. 2001).

25 ‘Abdallāh Ṣāliḥ al-‘Uthaymīn, *Muḥammad b. ‘Abd al-Wahhāb, The Man and his Works* (London: I.B. Tauris, 2009), 82.

26 al-‘Uthaymīn, *Muḥammad b. ‘Abd al-Wahhāb*, 97.

27 “Wa qad zāda fihi ba‘ḍ awlādihi ziyādatan ḥasana” – see ‘Abd al-‘Azīz b. Zayd al-Rūmī, Muḥammad Bultāji, Sayyid Ḥijāb (eds.), *Mu‘allaḥāt al-shaykh al-īmām Muḥammad b. ‘Abd al-Wahhāb* (Riyadh: Maktabat Ibn Taymiyya, 1976), 231.

al-asmā' wa-l-ṣifāt in “later Wahhabi literature”.²⁸ Her evidence is drawn from later sources too, such as Muḥammad b. ‘Abd al-Wahhāb’s student Ibn Ghannām (d. 1810).²⁹

There is some evidence that Muḥammad b. ‘Abd al-Wahhāb underlined his adherence to Ḥanbalī theological school, especially when he addressed the learned men.³⁰ According to ‘Abd al-Raḥmān (d. 1869), Muḥammad b. ‘Abd al-Wahhāb’s grandson, it was during his grandfather’s study with scholars in Basra that God revealed to him what was hidden to others, and what was the Sunni way in the Divine names and attributes and belief. Reportedly, this special divine inspiration set him apart from other scholars of his time and moved him to compose *Kitāb al-tawḥīd* on the basis of ḥadīth books, which he found in Basra.³¹ ‘Abd al-Raḥmān states that Muḥammad b. ‘Abd al-Wahhāb left Basra for al-Ahsa to seek learning with the most renowned scholars, among them also his cousin ‘Abdallāh b. Fayrūz.³² The latter had in his possession some books of both Ibn Taymiyya and Ibn al-Qayyim. Muḥammad b. ‘Abd al-Wahhāb, delighted by this fact, praised ‘Abdallāh b. Fayrūz for his knowledge of the doctrine of Aḥmad b. Ḥanbal. In al-Ahsa, he discussed with the local scholars some doctrinal mistakes of Ibn Ḥajar al-‘Asqalānī (d. 1449), a famous commentator on the *Ṣaḥīḥ al-Bukhārī*. He explained that Ash‘arīs contradicted al-Bukhārī’s position.³³

28 See Nahouza, *Wahhabism*, 62–63.

29 This source is Muḥammad b. ‘Abd al-Wahhāb, “Fatāwā wa-masā’il”, in *Mu‘allafāt al-Shaykh Muḥammad b. ‘Abd al-Wahhāb* (Riyadh: al-Markaz al-Islāmī lil-Ṭibā‘a wa-l-Nashr, 2010), vol. 4, 42–43. As Traboulsi points out considering Ibn Ghannām and other chroniclers of early Wahhābism, “[...] they were writing after the death of the Imam. In other words, they were writing with a long history of success and conquests in mind.” See Samer Traboulsi, “An Early Refutation of Muḥammad Ibn ‘Abd al-Wahhāb’s Reformist Views”, *WI* 42:3 (2002), 375.

30 See an apologetic on *tawḥīd al-asmā' wa-l-ṣifāt* by ‘Abd al-‘Azīz b. Muḥammad b. ‘Alī ‘Abd al-Laṭīf, *Da‘āwā al-munāwī‘īn li-da‘wat al-shaykh Muḥammad b. ‘Abd al-Wahhāb, ‘arḍ wa-naqḍ* (Riyadh: Dār Ṭayyiba, 1989), 113–16. The author admits, however, that the topic was debated after the conquest of Najd and by later scholars.

31 This particular passage is quoted by David Commins, *The Wahhabi Mission and Saudi Arabia* (London: I.B. Tauris, 2006), 12.

32 See ‘Abd al-Raḥmān b. Ḥasan b. ‘Abd al-Wahhāb, *al-Maqāmāt* (Riyadh: Dārat al-Malik ‘Abd al-‘Azīz, 2005), 66–68; and Muḥammad b. Ibrāhīm al-Shaybānī (ed.), *Tārīkh al-‘allāma qāḍī l-Kuwayt al-awwal fi l-Zubāra wa-l-Kuwayt Muḥammad b. ‘Abd al-Wahhāb b. Fayrūz al-Wuhaybī* (Kuwait: Manshūrāt Markaz al-Makhtū‘āt wa-l-Turāth wa-l-Wathā‘iq, 2016), 12. He was a son of Muḥammad Āl Fayrūz, who is considered to be the first judge of Kuwait. He was born in Ushayqir and died in al-Ahsa in 1761. ‘Abdallāh’s son Muḥammad exchanged some letters with Muḥammad b. ‘Abd al-Wahhāb and was at variance with him as regards the question of necrolatry.

33 ‘Abd al-Raḥmān, *al-Maqāmāt*, 67–68.

As far as we know, probably the first Wahhābī treatise that deals in depth with the Divine names and attributes was written after the death of Muḥammad b. ‘Abd al-Wahhāb. The treatise has been ascribed to Muḥammad b. Nāṣir al-Ḥāzīmī, a Yemeni student of Muḥammad al-Shawkānī and an advocate of Wahhābism, by scholars such as Ṣiddīq Ḥasan Khān (d. 1890) or Khayr al-Dīn al-Ziriklī (d. 1976).³⁴ According to Saudi editions of the book, however, its authorship is attributed to shaykh Ḥamad b. Nāṣir b. Mu‘ammar (d. 1811), a student of Muḥammad b. ‘Abd al-Wahhāb and Ibn Ghannām. We find this attribution plausible.³⁵ Ibn Mu‘ammar is known in Saudi history as a supervisor of Meccan *qāḍīs* after the Saudi conquest of Ḥijāz in 1805. According to one such edition, in 1796, Ghālīb b. Musā‘id, the sharīf of Mecca, requested that ‘Abd al-‘Azīz b. Muḥammad b. Su‘ūd send someone to engage in discussions on religious matters with local scholars of the Mālikī, Ḥanafī, and Shāfi‘ī schools.³⁶ Ibn Mu‘ammar, who was dispatched for this purpose, penned a response resulting from this inquiry.

Another telling example of a learned debate can be found in a letter from an early Wahhābī scholar Ḥamad b. ‘Atīq (d. 1883) addressed to Ṣiddīq Ḥasan Khān. The latter was one of the most learned Muslim scholars of the 19th century, who belonged to the Ahl al-ḥadīth movement of the Indian subcontinent. Ahl al-ḥadīth were influenced by the works of Ibn Taymiyya, Ibn al-Qayyim and al-Shawkānī, especially in claiming *ijtihād* in jurisprudence and, to some extent, also in their anti-Ash‘arī position in theology. Ṣiddīq’s *Fath al-bayān* ranks among the first printed commentaries on the Qur‘ān in the Islamic world (1290/1873 Bhopal print, 1300/1883 Būlāq print). In his letter,³⁷ Ḥamad b. ‘Atīq praises Ṣiddīq Ḥasan Khān for his new Quranic commentary, which reached him in 1298/1881. Nonetheless, he politely expresses his criticism of Ṣiddīq’s

34 See, for example, Siddīq Ḥasan Khān, *Abjad al-‘ulūm*, ed. ‘Abd al-Jabbār Zakkār (Damascus: Manshūrat Wizārat al-Thaqāfa, 1978), vol. 3, 200, and Khayr al-Dīn al-Ziriklī, *al-A‘lām* (Beirut: Dār al-‘Ilm lil-Malāyīn, 2002), vol. 7, 122. Regarding the uncertainty, see for instance ‘Abd al-Laṭīf, *Da‘āwā al-munāwī‘in li-da‘wat al-shaykh Muḥammad b. ‘Abd al-Wahhāb*, and the relevant note on pages 118 and 119.

35 See Ḥamad b. Nāṣir b. Mu‘ammar, *al-Tuḥfa al-madaniyya fi l-‘aqida al-salafiyya*, edited by ‘Abd al-Salām b. Barjas b. Nāṣir Āl ‘Abd al-Karīm (Riyadh: Dār al-‘Āshīma, 1992/93), and Ḥamad b. Nāṣir b. Mu‘ammar, *al-Fawākih al-‘idhāb fi mu‘taqad al-shaykh Muḥammad b. ‘Abd al-Wahhāb fi l-ṣifāt*, ed. ‘Abd al-Rahmān b. ‘Abdallāh al-Turkī, foreword by ‘Abdallāh b. ‘Abd al-Muḥsin al-Turkī, a minister of religious issues, propaganda and guidance of Saudi Arabia (Beirut: Mu‘assasat al-Risāla, third edition 1996).

36 Ibn Mu‘ammar, *al-Fawākih*, 26.

37 According to Preckel, the letter was written ca. 1880 – Claudia Preckel, “Screening Ṣiddīq Ḥasan Khān’s Library”, in *Islamic Theology, Philosophy and Law: Debating Ibn Taymiyya and Ibn Qayyim al-Jawziyya*, ed. Birgit Krawietz and Georges Tamer (Berlin, Boston: De Gruyter, 2013), 162–220.

misleading interpretation of the Divine names and attributes, especially God's transcendency and the verse of God's sitting on the throne (*uluww* and *istiwā'*). It is evident from the letter that Ḥamad b. 'Atīq was perfectly familiar with some important works of Ibn al-Qayyim and Ibn Taymiyya dealing with the topic of the Divine names and attributes. He mentions, for example, that parts of Ibn al-Qayyim's poem *Nūniyya* (a poem with a rhyme on the letter "n") are quite difficult. As there is no known explanation available to him, he suggests that Ṣiddīq Ḥasan Khān is the one who should make it.³⁸ Moreover, he would benefit from it in fighting heretics. In this regard, Ḥamad b. 'Atīq also recommends other books³⁹ which deal with the monotheism of the Divine names and attributes.⁴⁰ The fact that Ṣiddīq Ḥasan Khān was influenced by Ḥanbalī theology is evident in his book *Qaṭf al-thamr fī bayān 'aqīdat ahl al-athar*. According to Saudi scholarship, the shift in his attitude toward the Divine names and attributes was directly impacted by Ḥamad b. 'Atīq.⁴¹

However, in the Wahhābī scholarship of the second Saudi state, the topic of the Divine names and attributes had only a limited impact, largely due to a shortage of qualified teachers (though there were some exceptions, such as Ḥamad b. 'Atīq's son Sa'd, who was sent to India by his father). This changed significantly in the third Saudi state (the beginning of the modern era started with 'Abd al-'Azīz in 1902) as its political, ideological and economic power was on the rise.

Commentaries on *Kitāb al-tawḥīd* provide us with another insight into the (un)importance of the Divine names and attributes, how this topic evolved over time, and how the very conception of *tawḥīd* itself developed. It is evident from the early commentaries that their authors paid very little attention to this topic. Interestingly enough, in these commentaries one can find a different

38 However, the first Salafī commentaries were penned later, for example by a Najdī scholar Aḥmad b. Ibrāhīm b. 'Isā (d. 1911), Muḥammad Khalīl Harrās (d. 1975), an Egyptian member of Anṣār as-Sunna al-Muḥammadiyya, and a Saudi scholar al-Raḥmān b. Nāṣir al-Sa'dī (d. 1957), and also in audio lectures by his pupil shaykh al-'Uthaymīn. See 'Abd al-Raḥmān b. Nāṣir al-Sa'dī (ed.), *Tawḍīḥ al-kāfiyya al-shāfiyya fī l-intiṣār al-firqa al-nājiyya* (Riyadh: Aqḍwā' al-Salaf, first edition, 2000), 6.

39 Namely Ibn Taymiyya's *al-'Aql wa-l-naql* and *al-Tis'imīyya*, and Ibn al-Qayyim's *al-Ṣawā'iq al-mursala 'alā al-jahmiyya wa-l-mu'atṭila* and *al-Juyūsh al-Islāmiyya 'alā għazw al-mu'atṭila wa-l-jahmiyya*.

40 Ismā'īl b. Sa'd b. 'Atīq, *Hidāyat al-ṭariq min rasā'il wa-fatāwā al-shaykh Muḥammad b. 'Alī b. 'Atīq*, 112–29, cited also in 'Abd al-Raḥmān b. 'Abd al-Laṭīf b. 'Abdallāh Āl al-Shaykh, *Mashāhīr 'ulamā' Najd wa-ghayruhum* (Dār al-Yamāma, second edition, 1974), 245–54.

41 See the introduction in Muḥammad Ṣiddīq Ḥasan Khān al-Qannūjī, *Qaṭf al-thamr fī bayān 'aqīdat ahl al-athar*, ed. 'Āṣim b. 'Abdallāh al-Qaryūṭī (Riyadh: Jāmi'at al-Imām Muḥammad b. Su'ūd al-Islāmiyya).

tawhīd division than the one used today. It seems that scholars relied on Ibn al-Qayyim.⁴² This is hardly surprising considering the fact that he was a more intelligible and eloquent author than his teacher Ibn Taymiyya.

‘Abd al-‘Azīz’s Effort in Claiming Religious and Political Legitimacy

In 1923, a collection of Wahhābī treatises edited by prominent Najdī scholar Sulaymān b. Saḥmān (d. 1930) was published in Cairo by order of the Saudi ruler ‘Abd al-‘Azīz. The collection mostly includes treatises by Muḥammad b. ‘Abd al-Wahhāb, but also some of the editor’s own and those of his contemporaries, such as Muḥammad b. Abd al-Laṭīf Āl al-Shaykh (d. 1948) and Muḥammad Rashīd Riḍā (d. 1935). The collection is interesting for two reasons. First, it attests to the adjective “Wahhābī” as an endonym, while the present academic literature prefers to adopt the later Saudi narrative of a pejorative exonym. Second, as a whole, it subscribes to the teachings of Ibn Taymiyya. In the introduction, the editor decries the distortion of heretical Shī‘a and allegorical exegesis of the ignorant ones (*tahrīf al-ghālīn wa-ta’wīl al-jāhilīn*) according to prominent traditionalist (and all Ḥanbalī in theology⁴³) scholars of the Mamlūk period such as Ibn Taymiyya, Ibn al-Qayyim, al-Dhahabī, Ibn Kathīr (the latter three being Ibn Taymiyya’s pupils) and Ibn Rajab (d. 1393, himself a pupil of Ibn al-Qayyim).⁴⁴ Most of the treatises deal with the veneration of graves and various forms of polytheism. The fifth treatise, written by Muḥammad b. ‘Abd al-Laṭīf, deals among other things with *tawhīd*. Although it neither mentions Ibn Taymiyya’s typology of it nor mentions him by name, it seems – judging both from the formulations and content – that it depends

42 In one of the first commentaries on *Kitāb al-tawhīd*, entitled *Fatḥ al-Majīd*, ‘Abd al-Raḥmān, a grandson of Muḥammad b. ‘Abd al-Wahhāb, follows Ibn al-Qayyim’s dichotomic typology. Accordingly, he divides it into *tawhīd* of knowledge and affirmation (*tawhīd fī l-ma’rifā wa-l-iṭhābāt*) and *tawhīd* of devotion and intentions (*tawhīd fī l-ṭalab wa-l-qaṣd*). We find this dichotomic division in what is probably the oldest commentary on *Kitāb al-tawhīd* written by Ibn ‘Abd al-Wahhāb’s grandson Sulaymān, who attributes it to both Ibn al-Qayyim and Ibn Taymiyya. See Sulaymān b. ‘Abdallāh b. Muḥammad b. ‘Abd al-Wahhāb, *Taysīr al-‘azīz al-ḥamīd, sharḥ kitāb al-tawhīd*, ed. Usāma b. ‘Aṭāyā b. ‘Uthmān al-‘Utaybī (Riyadh: Dār al-Ṣumay‘ī, 2007), vol. 1, 120.

43 At least in medieval parlance, and of course such a statement has always been subject to narratives and counternarratives.

44 Sulaymān b. Saḥmān, ed., *al-Hadīyya al-saniyya wa-l-tuḥfa al-wahhābiyya li-jamī‘ ikhwāninā al-muwahḥidīn min ahl al-milla al-ḥanifiyya wa-l-ṭariqa al-muḥammadiyya* (Cairo: Maṭba‘at al-Manār, 1923/24), 3.

heavily on Ibn Taymiyya's teachings when it comes to the "belief in the Divine names and attributes".⁴⁵

It appears that the topic of the Divine names and attributes as a means of claiming "orthodoxy"⁴⁶ was promoted by the founder and later king of the third Saudi State. 'Abd al-'Azīz put much effort into the legitimization of the Wahhābī movement in the eyes of the Muslim audience, especially after his conquest of the more cosmopolitan Ḥijāz (1925) and subduing the rebellion of the Ikhwān movement (1930), whose zealotism and disobedience endangered his aspiration for international recognition. Because of the lack of learned Wahhābī scholars who could undertake such a difficult task at that time, he relied on cooperation with sympathetic Muslim intelligentsia abroad and by taking advantage of the printing press. Among the most prominent advocates of the Saudi mission were two scholars: an Iraqī Maḥmūd Shukrī al-Alūsī⁴⁷ and Rashīd Riḍā, born in Northern Lebanon and settled permanently in Cairo in 1897.

These scholars helped to strip Wahhābism of its "unorthodox" label⁴⁸ and connect it to the medieval Ḥanbalī school of theology and law. In his *Tārīkh Najd*, Maḥmūd Shukrī al-Alūsī (d. 1924) defined "Wahhābīs" as Salafīs on the basis that their beliefs are modelled on those of the early pious community. Moreover, he defined them as Sunnīs since their way is the way of Sunnīs. Importantly, he stated that they affirm the literal meaning of the Divine attributes in the Qur'ān and ḥadīth (*yuqirrūn āyāt al-ṣifāt wa-l-aḥādīth 'alā ḡāhirihā*). Here he explicitly mentioned the attribute of God's sitting on the throne (*istiwā'*), one of the most discussed theological issues of medieval Ḥanbalī/Salafī theologians. In law, he defined them quite soberly as Ḥanbalīs, who do not refuse *taqlīd*.⁴⁹

45 *al-Hadīyya al-saniyya*, 95.

46 As David Commins aptly puts it in his seminal work on the early history of Wahhābism, "Throughout its history, the Wahhabi mission has confronted a constant barrage of criticism from Muslims who considered it a heresy." See Commins, *The Wahhabi Mission*, 19.

47 Maḥmūd Shukrī al-Alūsī was the scion of a prominent scholarly family in Baghdad. His grandfather Maḥmūd Shihāb al-Dīn had composed a thirty-volume commentary on the Qur'ān, and his uncle Nu'mān Khayr al-Dīn wrote a seminal defense of Ibn Taymiyya. See Ahmed El Shamsy, *Rediscovering the Islamic Classics: How Editors and Print Culture Transformed an Intellectual Tradition* (Princeton: Princeton University Press, 2020), 174–75.

48 For instance, as early as 1809/10, the Ottoman Sultan issued a decree to his deputies in Baghdad and Damascus in which he ordered that the term "Wahhābī" be replaced with "Khārījī"; see 'Abd al-Raḥmān b. 'Abdallāh al-Shuqayr, *Tibā'at al-kutub wa-waqūfuhā 'inda al-malik 'Abd al-'Azīz: dirāsa taḥlīliyya wa-qā'ima bibliyūghrafīyya* (Riyadh: Dārat al-Malik 'Abd al-'Azīz, 2003), 35.

49 Maḥmūd Shukrī al-Alūsī, *Tārīkh Najd* (Cairo: al-Maṭba'a al-Salafiyya, 1925), 37, 48.

The crucial role of Rashīd Riḍā in promoting Wahhābī ideas is already well-documented by Lauzière. Rashīd Riḍā gained an international reputation as the editor of the Islamic magazine *al-Manār*. His opinions and articles on Wahhābīs, initially published in *al-Manār* and *al-Ahrām*, were later compiled and published together under the title *al-Wahhābiyyūn wa-l-Ḥijāz*. It is probable that he used the label “Wahhābīs” in the title of his book, as they were known by it in great Arab metropolises. Therein, he described Muḥammad b. ‘Abd al-Wahhāb as a follower of Ibn Taymiyya and Ibn al-Qayyim. Ibn Taymiyya was also praised as a proponent of the Salafī school (*madhhab al-salaf*) who was put to the test because of his interpretation of the Divine attributes. However, Rashīd Riḍā, in order to dissociate them from that label, described Wahhābīs as adherents of the Salafī school in doctrinal issues (*madhhab al-salaf fi l-‘aḳā’id*) and Ḥanbalīs in jurisprudence (*madhhab al-imām Aḥmad b. Ḥanbal fi l-furū’*).⁵⁰ In clarifying Salafī creed, Rashīd Riḍā drew from a treatise by sheikh ‘Abdallāh, one of the sons of Muḥammad b. ‘Abd al-Wahhāb, which had been published within *al-Hadiyya al-saniyya* shortly before. ‘Abdallāh wrote the treatise after the conquest of Mecca in 1218/1803 as an apologetic response to local scholars. In the treatise, ‘Abdallāh employs famous arguments of Ibn Taymiyya in his description of beliefs in the Divine names and attributes, such as God’s sitting on the throne.⁵¹ It is noteworthy that Rashīd Riḍā’s apologetic was also written in the context of the Saudi conquest of Mecca, this time in 1924.

The distinction made by Rashīd Riḍā between the two aspects of Ḥanbalī school is important for our argument. It stresses the fact that the methodology of the Salaf means a theological school, and we can surmise that the reason for this is that being Salafī in faith gave the school a wider currency. Moreover, they did not refer to Salaf for Wahhābī-Ḥanbalī jurisprudence, as the latter were followers of *taqlīd*, not *ijtihād*.⁵²

The role of print in transforming the monotheism of the Divine names and attributes into a crucial topic must be emphasized here. ‘Abd al-‘Azīz ordered many medieval Ḥanbalī and recent Wahhābī Islamic books to be published from the very beginning of his campaign. Until 1918, he had them printed exclusively in India. After the conquest of Ḥijāz in 1924, he had them printed in Cairo by al-Manār Press and al-Maktaba al-Salafiyya, and also in

50 Rashīd Riḍā, *al-Wahhābiyyūn wa-l-Ḥijāz: ṭā’ifa min maqālāt nushirat fi l-Manār wa-l-Ahrām* (Cairo: Maṭba’at al-Manār, 1925/26), 7.

51 Riḍā, *al-Wahhābiyyūn wa-l-Ḥijāz*, 11.

52 In Saudi religious literature, of course, one can encounter the narrative that Muḥammad b. ‘Abd al-Wahhāb was a *mujaddid* and a *mujtahid*, but this narrative has not been very sustainable. A critic of this view was, for example, Shaykh al-Albānī, who himself claimed *ijtihād*.

Mecca, where a branch of the publishing house named al-Maṭba‘a al-Salafiyya wa-Maktabatuhā was established due to the growing demand for Salafī books. The role of Mecca increased even more significantly after the creation of Saudi Arabia in 1932.⁵³

More specifically, the establishment of al-Maṭba‘a al-Salafiyya wa-Maktabatuhā in Mecca can provide another important insight into the growing role of print in defining Salafism. Lauzière, who studied the publishing house in relation to his interest in the idea of *salafiyya*, mentions that al-Maṭba‘a in Cairo published literature of various sorts that contradicted the most rationalist and liberal ideas of the reform movement, while the branch in Mecca published medieval Ḥanbalī texts.⁵⁴ He comments on this development by quoting Henri Laoust, who was struck by the rise of “neo-Hanbalite Puritanism”.

In this regard, it must be duly noted that ‘Abd al-‘Azīz was by no means the first to initiate interest in the works of Ibn Taymiyya and Ibn al-Qayyim. The process of interconnecting the teachings of Muḥammad b. ‘Abd al-Wahhāb with that of Ibn Taymiyya and Ibn al-Qayyim was not accomplished at that time. One of the most influential defenses of Ibn Taymiyya can be found in *Jalā’ al-‘aynayn fī muḥākamat al-Aḥmadayn*, written by Nu‘mān Khayr al-Dīn al-Alūsī and published in Cairo in 1881.⁵⁵ This book significantly shaped perceptions of Ibn Taymiyya in major Arab urban centers such as Baghdad, Damascus, and Cairo. Later on, the endeavor to collect the manuscripts of Ibn Taymiyya and Ibn al-Qayyim for printing was part of the movement known as enlightened *salafiyya*.⁵⁶ In 1908, for example, Maḥmūd Shukrī al-Alūsī, based in Baghdad, complained to his colleague in Damascus, Jamal al-Dīn al-Qāsimī (d. 1914), that the Ḥanbalīs in Najd were among the most incompetent in terms of the care given to the works of both scholars.⁵⁷ At any rate, as we can see from what was printed in Mecca, it is evident that the press focused on doctrinal issues (*‘aqīda*) and, in particular, on the topic of the Divine names and attributes.

53 We draw here from al-Shuqayr, *Ṭibā‘at al-kutub*, especially 77–81.

54 Henri Lauzière, “The Construction of *salafiyya*: Reconsidering Salafism from the Perspective of Conceptual History”, *IJMES* 42:3 (2010), 369–89.

55 Nafi, Basheer M., “Salafism Revived: Nu‘mān al-Alūsī and the Trial of Two Aḥmads”, *WI* 49:1 (2009), 49–97.

56 On the broader context of printing and its impact see especially El Shamsy, *Rediscovering the Islamic Classics*.

57 Muḥammad b. Nāṣir al-‘Ajāmī, ed., *al-Rasā‘il al-mutabādala bayna Jamāl al-Dīn al-Qāsimī wa-Maḥmūd Shukrī al-Alūsī* (Beirut: Dār al-Bashā‘ir al-Islāmiyya, 2001), 47.

a formal doxological formulation used by Ibn Taymiyya, which in years to come became a kind of Salafī statement. The point is that the committee in all likelihood published the creed so it could gain wider Sunnī currency, especially in comparison to Ibn Taymiyya's *al-'Aqīda al-wāsiṭiyya*, which was produced earlier in India within *Majmū'at al-tawḥīd*, a famous collection of Wahhābī treatises arranged together with older Ḥanbalī texts.⁶³

Salafī appropriation has become a common Saudi strategy in influencing Sunnī Muslims. It is noteworthy that according to Shiliwala, *al-'Aqīda al-ṭahāwīyya* has been published since that time in many editions. Salafis have substantially impacted Muslim discussions on subjects like the attributes of God and the validity of certain Ṣūfī practices, thereby placing non-Salafis on the defensive.⁶⁴

In other words, 'Abd al-'Azīz's rhetoric was meant to address a broader Muslim audience despite his effort to disseminate Ḥanbalī and Wahhābī literature. For example, on the occasion of the *ḥajj* in 1929, 'Abd al-'Azīz officially denied giving preference to any specific school of Islam. His speech was printed by the Saudi newspaper *Umm al-Qurā* as follows: "We are described as Wahhābis in order to give the impression that we have a separate school. This is a serious mistake born of hostile and malicious propaganda. Muḥammad b. 'Abd al-Wahhāb preached nothing new. We are thus not followers of a new school or a new dogma (*'aqīda*). Our doctrine is that of the pious early Muslim community (*al-salaf al-ṣāliḥ*), based on the Book of God and his Messenger, and on what they followed. We respect the four legal schools. In our eyes, there is no difference between Mālik, Shāfi'ī, Aḥmad, and Abū Ḥanīfa. We respect all of them."⁶⁵

We can take his words to mean that the way of the Salaf, i.e., the Ḥanbalī/Salafī creed, is the only acceptable creed, regardless of the adherence to a

Whoever Allah leads astray, there is none to guide him. I testify there is no God but Allah alone, without any partners, and that Muhammad, peace and blessings be upon him, is His servant and His messenger."

63 al-Shuqayr, *Ṭibā'at al-kutub*, 42. The collection published in India is not to be confused with *Majmū'at al-tawḥīd al-naǧdiyya* by Rashīd Riḍā, published in 1927. The latter contains, among other things, treatises on the theology of God's names and attributes, but only those authored by Wahhābī scholars. It is noteworthy that Ibn Bāz, when asked in 1991 to recommend the most important books on *'aqīda*, suggested *al-'Aqīda al-wāsiṭiyya* for beginners, as it briefly explains the trichotomic *tawḥīd* and Salafī creed. He adds that this creed was called upon by Muḥammad b. 'Abd al-Wahhāb and is the creed of the Saudi state. In general, he suggests, among other volumes, Ibn Abī l-'Izz's commentary on *al-'Aqīda al-ṭahāwīyya*. See *Majmū'at fatāwā wa-maqālāt*, vol. 7, 178–79.

64 Shiliwala, "Constructing a Textual Tradition", 462.

65 "Kḥiṭāb jalālat al-malik", *Umm al-Qurā* 229 (16 May 1929). This is a slightly modified translation of Nabil Mouline, *The Clerics of Islam: Religious Authority and Political Power in Saudi Arabia* (New Haven: Yale University Press, 2014), 111.

certain school of law. Or, as Nabil Mouline points out: “‘Abd al-‘Aziz profited from the presence of pilgrim delegations to affirm that Hanbalism-Wahhabism was only one of several expressions of the modern Muslim reformism known as al-Salafiyya, Salafism. In doing so, with the help of his Egyptian and Syrian advisors, he drew upon all of the reformists’ fondest catchwords and slogans: the dogma of the pious ancestors, the application of the Law, and the overcoming of distinction between the four legal schools of Islam.”⁶⁶ The last-mentioned point illustrates the fact that after he conquered Ḥijāz, ‘Abd al-‘Azīz abolished the separate congregations of the four schools of law in al-Masjid al-ḥarām. He unified the prayers under one imām and removed four sites (*maqāmāt al-a‘imma al-arba‘a*) that had previously marked the location for each school. The aspect of jurisprudence, however, is a more complex issue that we do not intend to deal with here, since in later developments the Ḥanbalī school of law prevailed, at least in domestic institutions.

‘Abd al-‘Azīz’s claim might have been a political one. In 1934/35, al-Fiqī published a brief apologetic in which he states that the label Wahhābīs is incorrect, as they are Ḥanbalīs both in jurisprudence and creed (*‘aqīda*). He argues that their teachings agree with the proper understanding of the Divine names and attributes; therefore, according to al-Fiqī Wahhābīs are apt to be called *al-da‘wa al-salafiyya al-muḥammadiyya* instead. Yet al-Fiqī opined that the most important part of the teachings of Muḥammad b. ‘Abd al-Wahhāb was concerned with worship (*tawḥīd al-ālihiyya wa-l-‘ibāda*).⁶⁷

It is interesting to note that a few years later, on the occasion of the *ḥajj* in 1939, ‘Abd al-‘Azīz stressed the trichotomic *tawḥīd al-rubūbiyya*, *tawḥīd al-ulūhiyya*, and *tawḥīd al-asmā’ wa-l-ṣifāt*.⁶⁸ Mouline claims that in Dār al-tawḥīd, established by the king ‘Abd al-‘Azīz in Taif in 1945, even Ash‘arī theology was taught,⁶⁹ which might give the impression that there had been some experiments with it in the school curricula. He draws this information from the biography of shaykh al-Bassām, who also studied at that time in two other faculties in Mecca: Faculty of al-sharī‘a and Faculty of Arabic language.⁷⁰

66 Mouline, *The Clerics of Islam*, 111. This, however, suggests that the label “Salafism” was already in use at that time to describe modern Muslim reformism, which is unlikely. What is documented from that period is the adjective form or a reference to the “way of the Salaf”. Therefore, it would be anachronistic to refer to “Salafism” as a modern phenomenon associated with Saudi proselytism, as defined in this article, during this early period.

67 al-Fiqī, *Athar al-da‘wa al-wahhābiyya*, 13.

68 As evidenced here: “Kalimat al-malik ‘Abd al-‘Azīz fi ḥajj ‘ām 1357h”. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=wPtToZObcX8>, 1:17–32.

69 Mouline, *The Clerics of Islam*, 112.

70 ‘Abdallāh b. ‘Abd alrahmān b. Ṣālih al-Bassām, *‘Ulamā’ Najd* (Riyadh: Dār al-‘āshima, 1998/99), vol. 1, 81–116.

However, the biography says that he studied creed in Mecca, under a certain shaykh ‘Alī Jabr, “who was a great scholar of creed, yet he was an Ash‘arī”, while his other teachers of creed were Salafis.⁷¹ The biography also mentions, among the overall subjects he studied, the trichotomic *tawḥīd* (*tawḥīd bi-anwā‘ihī al-thalātha*) in *Kitāb al-tawḥīd* and *Sharḥ al-ṭahāwīyya*.⁷² From this reference, we may conclude that the Salafī creed was dominant at that time.

Notably, one of the instructors at Dār al-tawḥīd, most of whom were from abroad, was ‘Abd al-Razzāq al-‘Afifī (d. 1994), a prominent leader of the Egyptian Anṣār al-Sunna al-Muḥammadiyya. al-‘Afifī, who disseminated the teachings of Ibn al-Jawziyya and Ibn Taymiyya, played an important role in assisting the Kingdom with the development of its educational system and in mentoring the next generation of domestic clerics. His contributions to teaching the monotheism of the Divine names and attributes, following his migration to Saudi Arabia in 1948/49, are highly regarded in Saudi scholarship.⁷³

The Salafī methodology of the Divine names and attributes based on Ibn Taymiyya seems to have become emphasized within Saudi Salafism as Saudi Arabia made contact with non-Wahhābī scholars, and religion gradually became institutionalized, more specifically at the end of ‘Abd al-‘Azīz’s reign. However, its significance greatly increased owing to the influential efforts of Saudi Pan-Islamic organizations, exemplified by institutions like the Islamic University of Madinah in the 1960s.

It was also ‘Abd al-‘Azīz who created the office of Grand Muftī, which was first held by Muḥammad b. Ibrāhīm Āl al-Shaykh in 1953–1969. Among his responsibilities as the Grand Muftī was the state censorship of religious literature. In a letter dated 4 Jumada I 1378 (16 November 1958) he asked Fayṣal, then prime minister and crown prince, to allocate one million riyals for publishing Salafī literature.⁷⁴ As is evidenced in his personal correspondence, Muḥammad b. Ibrāhīm was not opposed to financing non-Ḥanbalī books of jurisprudence. Yet he was careful not to promote books that were not in accordance with Salafī (i.e., Ḥanbalī) methodology in the Divine names and attributes. Thus, he laconically stated about a certain book by a Deobandi

71 al-Bassām, *‘Ulamā’ Najd*, vol. 1, 92.

72 al-Bassām, *‘Ulamā’ Najd*, vol. 1, 93.

73 He was a teacher of shaykh al-Fawzān, al-‘Uthaymīn, and Ibn Jibrīn, to name just a few. See Aḥmad b. ‘Alī al-Zāmīlī ‘Asīrī, *Manhaj al-shaykh ‘Abd al-Razzāq al-‘Afifī wa-juhūdūhu fī taqrīr al-‘aqīda wa-l-radd ‘alā l-mukhālīfīn* (MA thesis, Riyadh: Jāmi‘at al-Imām Muḥammad b. Su‘ūd al-Islāmiyya, 2010).

74 Muḥammad b. ‘Abd al-Raḥmān b. Qāsim, ed., *Fatāwā wa-rasā’il samāḥat al-shaykh Muḥammad b. Ibrāhīm b. ‘Abd al-Latīf Āl al-Shaykh* (Mecca: Maṭba‘at al-Ḥukūma, 1979), vol. 13, “al-Maktabāt wa-l-mu‘allafāt”, 113.

scholar Idrīs al-Kandahlāwī: “There are many errors in the terms of doctrine, as the author holds Ash‘arī views. Therefore, it should not be supported for publication.”⁷⁵ In contrast, he paid much more attention to a book named *‘Uddat al-muslimīn fī ma‘ānī l-fātiḥa wa-qīṣār al-suwar* published by Muḥammad Maḥmūd al-Ṣawwāf, an influential religious scholar, in 1968.⁷⁶ On 28 Rajab 1389 (17 October 1969) he wrote two letters, one addressed to the king and the other to the author himself. In the former, he mentioned that the book contains Jahmī (i.e., heretical) views on the Divine names and attributes and, given the importance of this issue, the Muslim community must be informed and distance themselves from such errors. In the latter, the Grand Muftī rebuked – politely, but quite vehemently – al-Ṣawwāf, for he erroneously drew from a Rāfiḍī (i.e., Shī‘ī) exegete of the Qur‘ān who had previously been harshly denounced by Ibn Taymiyya. He therefore expounded at length on the monotheism of the Divine names and attributes according to the proper methodology of the Salaf, which was evidently based on Ibn Taymiyya’s arguments.⁷⁷ In another letter dated 17 Sha‘bān 1389 (29 October 1969), shaykh Muḥammad b. Ibrāhīm explains to al-Ṣawwāf more explicitly that the problem is not only that he is drawing from a Shī‘ī author, but that he was spreading incorrect views about the Divine names and attributes. The Grand Muftī therefore urged al-Ṣawwāf to denounce his erroneous views in this regard in all local newspapers.⁷⁸

Instrumentalizing Ibn Taymiyya against the Ash‘arīs and in Reassessing “Salafī-ness”

If the topic of the Divine names and attributes is supposed to be a distinctive characteristic for Salafism, what then is the typology based on this criterion? To our knowledge, the Salafī scholar ‘Abd al-Raḥmān al-Sa‘dī (d. 1956) was probably the first commentator of *Kitāb al-tawḥīd* (given its importance, we narrowed the research to focus on this book in particular) to use Ibn Taymiyya’s trichotomic division of *tawḥīd*. Still, he used it in the reverse order to the one used

75 Qāsim, *Fatāwā*, vol. 13, 121.

76 Ṣawwāf is considered to be a founding member of the Muslim brotherhood in Iraq. He was exiled to Saudi Arabia, where he became a professor at the faculty of Sharī‘a at the Umm al-Qurā University in Mecca and adviser at the education ministry of Saudi Arabia. See Chanfī Ahmed, *West African ‘ulamā’ and Salafism in Mecca and Medina: Jawab al-Ifriqī, the Response of the African* (Leiden: Brill, 2015), 152.

77 Qāsim, *Fatāwā*, vol. 13, 128–42.

78 Qāsim, *Fatāwā*, vol. 13, 143.

preferentially today.⁷⁹ al-Sa'dī divided people according to their understanding of the Divine names and attributes into three groups: monotheistic believers (*mu'min muwahhid*), anthropomorphists (*mushabbih*), and transcendentalists (*mu'aṭṭil*).⁸⁰ The term *muwahhid* has been a well-known endonym of Wāhhābīs, distinguishing them from polytheists (*mushrik*), a term used in the early Wāhhābī writings mostly for Shī'īs, accused of necrolatry. However, al-Sa'dī used the term *muwahhid* in a theological sense. The other two terms are adopted from medieval theological parlance. *Tashbih*, a pejorative term in Islamic theology, denotes a heretical understanding of the Divine names and attributes both literally and in resemblance to material things. *Ta'ṭīl*, in turn, means a theological approach that denudes God of anthropomorphic characteristics to avoid anthropomorphism and even polytheism (*shirk*). Historically, this was an approach of Jahmiyya and Mu'tazila.⁸¹ Ibn Taymiyya, in his definition of the correct methodology of the monotheism of the Divine names and attributes, stated that the true believer must understand them literally but without anthropomorphizing and similarities. This, however, is a simplification of his position, to which he devoted thousands of pages of learned discussion, yet he was often unjustly accused of being an anthropomorphist himself, for he condemned the allegorical interpretation (*ta'wīl*) of the most blatant anthropomorphic attributes (e.g., the hand) as was adopted by the Ash'arī school.

In the Wāhhābī context, there is textual evidence that the terms “mu'aṭṭila” and “Ash'arīs” were used almost interchangeably in various editions of *Kitāb al-tawhīd* by Ibn 'Abd al-Wāhhāb, so al-Sa'dī's category of “transcendentalists” does not exclude Ash'arīs.⁸² al-Sa'dī's approach, influenced by his erudition and his deep insight⁸³ into Ibn Taymiyya's work, culminated in his disciple,

79 See al-Murtaḍā al-Zayn Aḥmad, ed., *Kitāb al-tawhīd lil-imām wa-l-mujaddid Muḥammad b. 'Abd al-Wāhhāb wa-Kitāb al-qawl al-sadīd fī maqāsid tawhīd lil-shaykh 'Abd al-Raḥmān b. Nāṣir al-Sa'dī* (Riyadh: Majmū'at al-Tuḥaf al-Nafā'is al-Dawliyya, 1996), 18. For his opinion on God's names and attributes, see 'Abd al-Razzāq b. 'Abd al-Ḥasan al-'Abbād, *al-Shaykh 'Abd al-Raḥmān al-Sa'dī wa-juhūduhu fī tawḍīḥ al-'aqīda* (Riyadh: Maktabat al-Rushd, 1993, second edition), 107–51.

80 al-'Abbād, *al-Shaykh 'Abd al-Raḥmān al-Sa'dī*, 109.

81 That is why Mu'tazila is called Ahl al-tawhīd in medieval theological literature, a term which was later appropriated by Wāhhābīs/Salafīs.

82 See, for example, Sulaymān b. 'Abdallāh b. Muḥammad b. 'Abd al-Wāhhāb, *Taysīr al-'azīz al-ḥamīd*, 170, who reads “affirmation of the attributes contrary to the Ash'arīs” (*ithbāt al-ṣifāt khilāfan lil-ash'ariyya*), while 'Abd al-Raḥmān b. Ḥasan Āl al-Shaykh, *Faṭḥ al-majīd sharḥ Kitāb al-tawhīd* (Cairo: al-Madānī, n.d.), 83, renders it “affirmation of the attributes contrary to the mu'aṭṭila” (*ithbāt al-ṣifāt khilāfan lil-mu'aṭṭila*).

83 As stressed in *Majmū'at mu'allafāt al-shaykh al-'allāma 'Abd al-Raḥmān al-Sa'dī*, ed. by Muḥammad b. 'Abd al-Raḥmān al-Sa'dī et al. (Riyadh: al-Dār al-'Arabiyya, 2011), vol. 1, 56.

Muḥammad b. Šālīḥ al-‘Uthaymīn (1929–2001).⁸⁴ The latter emulates entirely Ibn Taymiyya’s trichotomic division of *tawḥīd*, and even his polemic style recalls the “orthodox kalām” of Ibn Taymiyya. In this context, it is noteworthy that al-Matroudi, who studied the influence of Ibn Taymiyya on Ḥanbalī law, notes that al-‘Uthaymīn was influenced to a considerable degree by his teacher al-Sa‘dī, who was himself significantly affected by Ibn Taymiyya. al-‘Uthaymīn studied various subjects under al-Sa‘dī, such as creed, interpretation of the Qur’ān, ḥadīth, and jurisprudence and its general principles.⁸⁵

al-‘Uthaymīn, however, used the term Salafīs (*salafīyyūn*) instead of “monotheistic believers” in the parlance of al-Sa‘dī. In his opinion, Salafīs represent the only acceptable theological Sunnī school. Accordingly, he argued that other theological schools, namely Ash‘arīs and Māturīdīs, do not belong to Sunnī Muslims (*ahl al-sunna wa-l-jamā‘a*): “Whoever thinks that Sunnīs consist of three: Salafīs (*salafīyyūn*), Ash‘arīs and Māturīdīs, is wrong. This is an error.”⁸⁶ On the other hand, Ibn Bāz did not seem to hold such a strict position. He claimed that Ash‘arīs do not belong to Sunnīs only in the field of the Divine names and attributes, owing to their general allegorical interpretation, while in other aspects they do.⁸⁷

The Saudi religious scholars and other Salafīs not only modelled their teachings on Ibn Taymiyya in regard to the basic typology of *tawḥīd* and the Divine names and attributes; they also adopted his arguments against the Ash‘arīs. This trend continued in the 1960s, when Saudi Arabia faced the threat of Arab revolutionary nationalism (Nasserism), which aimed to overthrow Arab monarchist regimes. Under the leadership of King Fayṣal (1964–1975), Saudi Arabia responded by creating a pan-Islamic ideology out of local Wahhābism. This struggle must also be seen in the context of the mutual rivalry between mostly Ash‘arī al-Azhar under nationalist control on one hand and monarchist Saudi Arabia and its religious institutions on the other.⁸⁸ The most prominent

84 For more about al-‘Uthaymīn’s view on God’s attributes, see especially Mohammad Gharaibeh, *Zur Attributenlehre der Wahhābīyya unter besonderer Berücksichtigung der Schriften Ibn ‘Uṭaimīns (1929–2001)* (Berlin EB-Verlag, 2012).

85 Abdul Hakim I. Al-Matroudi, *The Ḥanbalī School of Law and Ibn Taymiyyah, Conflict or Conciliation* (London: Routledge, 2006), 162–70.

86 See Muḥammad al-Šālīḥ al-‘Uthaymīn, *Sharḥ al-‘Aqīda al-wāsiṭīyya li-shaykh al-imām Ibn Taymiyya*, ed. Sa‘d b. Fawwāz al-Šamīl (Dammam: Dār Ibn al-Jawzī, sixth edition, 2000/2001), vol. 1, 53. Similarly in Muḥammad b. Šālīḥ al-‘Uthaymīn, *al-Qawl al-mufīd ‘alā Kitāb al-tawḥīd* (Riyadh: Dār al-‘Āšima, n.d.), 14.

87 https://binbaz.org.sa/fatwas/20154/بيان_فرقة_الأشاعرة (last accessed 11 April 2024).

88 For more on the topic of the rivalry between Saudi Arabia and Egypt (and also Iran, for that matter), see, in particular, Masooda Bano and Keiko Sakurai, eds., *Shaping Global Islamic Discourses: The Role of al-Azhar, al-Medina and al-Mustafa* (Edinburgh: Edinburgh University Press, 2017). For an “analytical portrait” of Saudi global proselytizing activities

representatives of this ideological approach were ‘Abd al-‘Azīz b. Bāz and Muḥammad b. Ṣāliḥ al-‘Uthaymīn. The former held the most important religious positions in the country until his death.⁸⁹

In general, one of the most frequently used arguments was that Ash‘arīs have misinterpreted the eponym of the school. According to them, al-Ash‘arī went through two theological phases in his life: a period of being a rationalist Mu‘tazilī, and a period in which he adopted a position of compromise in the question of the Divine names and attributes between the position of traditionalists (*ahl al-ḥadīth*), who understood anthropomorphic descriptions literally but abhorred any resort to allegoric interpretation, and those who interpreted them allegorically in order to avoid accusations of anthropomorphism, that is the Mu‘tazilis or *al-mu‘aṭṭila*, who denied them as such. In the second period, al-Ash‘arī admitted a certain degree of metaphorical interpretation, especially in the case of the most blatant anthropomorphic descriptions, such as God’s hand. Ash‘arīs also adopted and further developed a theological method of *tafwīd*, a doctrine stating that the meanings of the ambiguous verses of the Qur‘ān should be consigned to God alone.

Ibn Taymiyya, however, argued that al-Ash‘arī went through not just two, but three periods, as is attested in his mature and final theological treatise of *al-Ibāna fī uṣūl al-diyāna*, neglected by the Ash‘arīs, and abandoned his previous compromise and returned to the right way of Aḥmad b. Ḥanbal and the Salaf.⁹⁰ According to this argument adapted by today’s Salafīs, the mainstream Ash‘arī school with its religious institutions, scholarship and authority falsely ascribe themselves to the eponym of the school. Salafīs are thus superior and the only legitimate theological school. The down-to-earth aspect of these theological polemics lay in discrediting Ash‘arī scholarship with its institutions (al-Azhar, among others) and religious authority while promoting Saudi religious authority both in jurisprudential issues and its political agenda.

Another illustration of the instrumentalization and manipulation of Saudi Salafism is assessing, often retrospectively and anachronistically, the “Salafi-ness” of prominent “Salafīs” in the broadest meaning of the word by implementing Ibn Taymiyya’s narrow understanding of the theology of the Divine names and attributes as a crucial criterion. In other words, the doctrinal

see Peter Mandaville, ed., *Wahhabism and the World: Understanding Saudi Arabia’s Global Influence on Islam* (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2022), especially the chapter written by Reinhard Schulze concerning “Transnational Wahhabism: The Muslim World League and the World Assembly of Muslim Youth”, 93–113.

89 President of the Islamic University of Madinah from 1970, head of the Council of Senior Scholars from 1972, Grand Muftī from 1993.

90 Aḥmad b. Ḥanbal himself belonged to the third and last generation of Salaf.

views of non-Ḥanbalī scholars of various historical periods and backgrounds, such as al-Shawkanī, Ṣiddīq Ḥasan Khān, Rashīd Riḍā, or Nāṣir al-Dīn al-Albānī (d. 1999), to name just a few, were sometimes put under scrutiny in the academic environment in order to assess, among other things, whether they were in congruence with the theological view of Ibn Taymiyya.

al-Shawkānī (d. 1834)⁹¹ was one of the most influential scholars of his day. As he was educated in Zaydī religious scholarship, he was quite independent of the Sunnī madhhabī system. In his vision of Sunnī Islām based primarily on ḥadīth (*ahl al-ḥadīth*), he was highly influenced by Ibn Taymiyya, especially in claiming *ijtihād* and fighting heresies (*bid'a*). He was critical of the mainstream Ash'arī school, yet his theological opinions were not Ḥanbalī in the narrow sense of Ibn Taymiyya. Because of his erudition and fame, he is often quoted in early Wahhābī literature, such as in early Wahhābī commentaries on *Kitāb al-tawḥīd* in support of Muḥammad b. 'Abd al-Wahhāb's teachings. His "Salafi-ness", however, was examined by Saudi scholarship, especially in regard to the Divine names and attributes. This was the case of a book entitled *Manhaj al-imām al-Shawkānī fī l-'aqīda*, which was published in Saudi Arabia in 1994 and originated from a PhD dissertation defended at the Islamic University of Madinah. The author, for example, comments on al-Shawkānī's treatise *al-Tuḥaf fī madhhab al-salaf*⁹² and compares it with Ibn Taymiyya's views. He mentions that the treatise makes an impression that al-Shawkānī is *mufawwiḍ* (that is, a follower of *tafwīḍ*), which is not the case.⁹³ He comes to the conclusion that he is a Salafī and not a *mufawwiḍ*, with the exception of his understanding of the attribute of Divine immanence (*ma'īyya*), which is not correct.⁹⁴ Ṣiddīq Ḥasan Khān, himself influenced by al-Shawkānī and a teacher of some early Wahhābī scholars, also became a subject of scrutiny in terms of his theological opinions on the Divine names and attributes, as is evidenced by a PhD dissertation defended at the Saudi Umm al-Qurā university in 1987.⁹⁵

Furthermore, we can mention the case of Rashīd Riḍā, also a highly influential thinker in many regards. Shaykh al-Uthaymīn ranks him among those who influenced him significantly, even though he was wrong in some

91 For his life and teachings, see Bernard Haykel, *Revival and Reform in Islam: The Legacy of Muhammad al-Shawkani* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2003).

92 The treatise itself was published as Muḥammad al-Shawkānī, *al-Tuḥaf fī madhhab al-salaf*, ed. Sayyid 'Āṣim 'Alī (Tanta: Dār al-Ṣaḥāba lil-Turāth, 1989).

93 'Abdallāh Numuk, *Manhaj al-imām al-Shawkānī fī l-'aqīda* (Riyadh: Maktabat Dār al-Qalam wa-l-Kitāb, 1994), 370.

94 Numuk, *Manhaj al-imām al-Shawkānī*, 375.

95 Akhtar Jamāl Muḥammad Luqmān, *al-Sayyid Ṣiddīq Ḥasan al-Qannūjī: āra'uhu al-i'tiqādiyya wa-mawqifuhu min 'aqīdat al-salaf* (PhD dissertation, Mecca: Umm al-Qurā, 1987).

aspects of his thought.⁹⁶ Egyptian scholar Khālid b. Fawzī concludes in his Master's thesis,⁹⁷ defended in 1987 in Saudi Arabia, that Rashīd Riḍā was a Salafi in the theology of the Divine names and attributes in comparison with Ḥasan al-Bannā, who followed the approach of Ash'arīs, that is *tafwīd*.⁹⁸ Tāmir Maḥmūd Mutawallī provides perhaps a more nuanced view on Rashīd Riḍā's thought in his Master's thesis, defended at the Islamic University of Madinah in 2000.⁹⁹ In the introduction, the author makes it clear that Muḥammad b. 'Abd al-Wahhāb and Ibn Taymiyya are the most renowned proponents of the methodology of the Salaf.¹⁰⁰ Yet, only part of the study is devoted to the Divine names and attributes. According to the author, Rashīd Riḍā was at first an Ash'arī, but after studying Ibn Taymiyya's books, he recognized that the methodology of the Salaf was the true way.¹⁰¹

Another example of this academic approach and retrospective thinking is Muḥammad b. 'Abdallāh al-Salmān's book *al-Shaykh Rashīd Riḍā al-salafī al-muṣliḥ*. In it, al-Salmān evaluates the "Salafī-ness" (*salafīyya*) of both Riḍā and *al-Manār*. According to al-Salmān, the journal's goal was to reform *al-'aqīda*, particularly by opposing necrolatry, superstitions, and advocating for the "way of the Salaf" in matters of the Divine names and attributes, while also criticizing *taqlīd*.¹⁰²

These are just few examples to underscore the significance of this topic of ideological scrutiny and verification, especially within various Islamic universities and institutions.

Conclusion

The Saudi religious establishment gradually adopted a trichotomic conception of *tawḥīd* modelled on the teachings of the medieval Ḥanbalī scholar Ibn Taymiyya. This adaptation was part of the broader transition from local

96 See *Qiṣṣati fī ṭalab al-'ilm*, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=5ZoTbV2gp5s> (26:30).

97 Khālid b. Fawzī b. 'Abd al-Ḥamīd Āl Ḥamza, *Muḥammad Rashīd Riḍā, Tawd wa-islāḥ, da'wa wa-dā'iyya. Jihād fī khidmat al-'aqīda wa-āthāruhu fī l-mujtama'āt al-fikriyya al-mu'āshira* (Alexandria: Dār 'Ulamā' al-Salaf, 1994/95, originally an MA thesis defended in 1987 at al-Ma'had al-'Āli li-I'dād al-A'imma wa-l-Du'āt, Mecca).

98 Khālid b. Fawzī, *Muḥammad Rashīd Riḍā*, 350–51.

99 Published as Tāmir Maḥmūd Mutawallī, *Manhaj al-shaykh Muḥammad Rashīd Riḍā fī l-'aqīda* (Jeddah: Dār Mājid 'Asīrī, 2004).

100 See Mutawallī, *Manhaj*, 7–8.

101 Mutawallī, *Manhaj*, 325.

102 Muḥammad b. 'Abdallāh al-Salmān, *al-Shaykh Rashīd Riḍā al-salafī al-muṣliḥ* (Riyadh: Ministry of Education and the Imam Mohammad Ibn Saud Islamic University, 1993), 51.

Wahhābism to global Salafism, through which the establishment sought to assert its religious and political legitimacy, claiming religious authority and even superiority. In our analysis, we have concentrated on the specific aspect of the monotheism of the Divine names and attributes (*tawḥīd al-asmā' wa-l-ṣifāt*), while leaving other aspects of *tawḥīd* aside.¹⁰³

In early Wahhābī scholarship, the issue of the Divine names and attributes was relatively marginal. However, as Saudi religious scholars became more advanced and engaged with the teachings of Ibn Taymiyya and Ibn al-Qayyim – whose arguments they used against their religious rivals – this topic became central and defining. Over time, the theology of Ibn Taymiyya became foundational in assessing an individual's "Salafī-ness", and his trichotomic conception of *tawḥīd* emerged as a key tool for the appropriation of the Islamic legacy (*turāth*).

Nonetheless, this evolution was gradual rather than an immediate transformation attributed to a single individual. We began by examining the teachings of Muhammad b. Abd al-Wahhāb and early Wahhābism to provide some context. Our focus then shifted to the rebranding of Wahhābism during the era of the third Saudi state, emphasizing the pivotal role of 'Abd al-'Azīz ibn Su'ūd and the significant influence of print media, as well as non-Saudi scholars, in this process. We further explored the role of institutionalization and the contributions of Saudi scholars during this evolution and also within the context of anti-Ash'arī polemics, which arose in response to the threats of Arab nationalism and anti-monarchism. One of the final trajectories we examined was connected to shaykh al-Sa'dī, the first Saudi scholar to deal in depth with the teachings of Ibn Taymiyya and Ibn al-Qayyim. al-Sa'dī's influence is especially evident in the case of his student, al-'Uthaymīn, with whom the transformation seems to have reached completion.¹⁰⁴ The worldwide spread of the trichotomic conception was then enabled by the emergence of Saudi Pan-Islamic organizations in the 1960s.

Salafism is a modern phenomenon and an ideological construct. To fully comprehend this phenomenon, it is essential to explore the debates among modern Salafīs themselves concerning what it means to be a Salafī or the

103 We dealt with the instrumentalization and ideologization of *tawḥīd al-ulūhiyya* in Ondřej Beránek and Pavel Ťupek, *The Temptation of Graves in Salafī Islam: Iconoclasm, Destruction and Idolatry* (Edinburgh: Edinburgh University Press, 2018).

104 al-'Uthaymīn published his first book, *Fatḥ rabb al-bariyya bi-talkhiṣ al-ḥamawīyya*, in 1962 – see Muḥammad b. Ṣāliḥ al-'Uthaymīn, *Sharḥ al-'aqīda al-wāsiṭiyya* (Dammam: Dār ibn al-Jawzī, 2010) vol. 1, 10. If we look at the contemporary textbooks used to teach *tawḥīd* at the Islamic University of Madinah, we find that the majority of them are commentaries written by al-'Uthaymīn; see <https://iu.edu.sa/itqan-course-3011> عقد.

opposite, even retrospectively. This issue largely revolves around theological debates related to *tawhīd al-asmā' wa-l-ṣifāt*, which has emerged as the singular, stable defining criterion, while other aspects of *tawhīd* are subject to variation, influenced by the internal agendas of various Salafī movements and interpretations. The same principle applies to one's adherence to a particular school of law and the assertion of *ijtihād*, aspects on which Salafīs often diverge.¹⁰⁵

¹⁰⁵ This work was partially supported by the European Regional Development Fund project 'Beyond Security: Role of Conflict in Resilience-Building' (reg. no.: CZ.02.01.01/00/22_008/0004595).